

THE FUTURE OF ENGLISH

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Annotation: What role does advertising play in the evolution of languages and the relationship between language and cultural knowledge? Using the example of the well-known Heineken slogan, 'Heineken refreshes the parts other beers cannot reach', David Crystal explained how this initial phrase evolved with the help of word play. Over 30 years, the phrase came to represent an ad campaign with 300 variations on the same phrase, with the word 'parts' substituted with everything from 'parrots' to 'pilots' to 'poets'.

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English in the world today

English is currently the most spoken language across the globe, with roughly 2.3 billion people speaking it as a first or additional language.

We have established a long-term research agenda into the future of the English language and its uses, needs, and demands worldwide and the forces driving them.

A language's development reflects the power of those who speak it

So how exactly did that happen? How did English grow so quickly and seemingly so unexpectedly? According to Crystal, in spite of the widespread notion that this is due, at least in part, to the fact that it is an easy language to learn, 'without any grammar', as some people have said, there is something much deeper behind the exponential growth of English as a global language. Crystal suggests that a language's development is a direct reflection of the power of those who speak it. From the beginnings of the British Empire, to the industrial revolution in Britain, which brought significant technological and scientific developments and a number of influential inventions from English-speaking inventors, through to the continued economic power of the 19th century and cultural power of the 20th century, English has maintained its edge.

New Englishes

The term "New Englishes" refers to regional and national varieties of the English language used in places where it is not the mother tongue of the majority of the population. The phrase is also known as new varieties of English, non-native varieties of English, and non-native institutionalized varieties of English.

New Englishes have certain formal properties—lexical, phonological, and grammatical—that differ from those of British or American standard English. Examples of New Englishes include Nigerian English, Singapore English, and Indian English.

Examples and Observations

"Most adaptation in a New English relates to vocabulary, in the form of new words (borrowings—from several hundred language sources, in such areas as Nigeria), word-formations, word-meanings, collocations, and idiomatic phrases. There are many cultural domains likely to motivate new words, as speakers find themselves adapting the language to meet fresh communicative needs."

One way of predicting the future is to look back at the past. The global role English plays today as a lingua franca – used as a means of communication by speakers of different languages – has parallels in the Latin of pre-modern Europe.

Having been spread by the success of the Roman Empire, Classical Latin was kept alive as a standard written medium throughout Europe long after the fall of Rome. But the Vulgar Latin used in speech continued to change, forming new dialects, which in time gave rise to the modern Romance languages: French, Spanish, Portuguese, Romanian and Italian.

Similar developments may be traced today in the use of English around the globe, especially in countries where it functions as a second language. New “interlanguages” are emerging, in which features of English are mingled with those of other native tongues and their pronunciations.

Despite the Singaporean government’s attempts to promote the use of Standard British English through the Speak Good English Movement, the mixed language known as “Singlish” remains the variety spoken on the street and in the home.

Spanglish, a mixture of English and Spanish, is the native tongue of millions of speakers in the United States, suggesting that this variety is emerging as a language in its own right.

Meanwhile, the development of automatic translation software, such as Google Translate, will come to replace English as the preferred means of communication employed in the boardrooms of international corporations and government agencies.

So the future for English is one of multiple Englishes.

Looking back to the early 20th century, it was the Standard English used in England, spoken with the accent known as “Received Pronunciation”, that carried prestige.

But today the largest concentration of native speakers is in the US, and the influence of US English can be heard throughout the world: can I get a cookie, I’m good, did you eat, the movies, “skedule” rather than “shedule”. In the future, to speak English will be to speak US English. US spellings such as disk and program are already preferred to British equivalents disc and programme in computing. The dominance of US usage in the digital world will lead to the wider acceptance of further American preferences, such as favorite, donut, dialog, center.

Some have questioned whether the increasing development and adoption of emoji pictograms, which allow speakers to communicate without the need for language, mean that we will cease to communicate in English at all? ;-)

The fast-changing world of social media is also responsible for the coining and spreading of neologisms, or “new words”. Recent updates to Oxford Dictionaries give a flavour: mansplaining, awesomesauce, rly, bants, TL;DR (too long; didn’t read).

One doesn’t need to be a world traveller to see that the English language spoken in India does not sound the same as the English language spoken in England. By the same token, the English language in Nairobi does not sound the same as the English language in New York.

And in India, Indian English is becoming less monolithic, meaning that the variety of English spoken in Bangalore differs slightly from that spoken in New Delhi. The New Delhi English is

influenced primarily by Hindi and is often referred to as Hinglish, while the Bangalore English is influenced by Kannada (which is Bangalore's local language) and is often referred to as Kanglish. So now we have several varieties of English being used within India, and while all of these are closer to British English than to American English, in recent years we've seen younger generations showing an increasing bias towards Americanisms. Despite all its variations, Indian English remains undoubtedly English.

In Kenya, both Swahili and English are official languages. But in Nairobi and other urban areas we're seeing a creole slang known as Sheng. Sheng has strong ties to Kenyan pop culture and this slang has emerged as a means for young people to communicate in code. In Sheng, for example the word for trousers is longi, which is derived from the English word long.

Languages are changing constantly. But the one that we, arguably, are most influenced by is English. From Old to Middle English, Early Modern to Late Modern, English has had the most documented changes out of many languages. How will this continue? With so many technological advances, more accessible travel and easier connections between international people through social media, English is bound to change immensely throughout the coming years. To be able to speculate how the English language might change in the future, we need to understand how it has changed in the past. Change can be repetitive. Technological advances have always brought new vocabulary with them. Considering that the speed of technological innovations is increasing dramatically at the moment, we can expect numerous new words being invented. Of course, new words aren't always necessary; old words can simply take on another meaning. For more information on language change.

Furthermore, more accessible travel will affect the amount of variations of English we have worldwide. It will be easier for people to travel to more isolated regions and spread their accent or dialect. In general, it would be easiest if everyone learnt English, as it would remove language barriers. Even now, there are more second-language English speakers worldwide than native ones. Maybe, in the future, there will be a lingua franca dialect? We can see this "phenomenon" in International Schools – pretty much every student, in any International School, in any country, has the same "International School accent", a mixture between an American and a British accent.

A similar effect can be seen through social media. It allows us to connect with international people – no matter where in the world, and therefore removes that geographical isolation that English speakers used to have. The only issue is that there is still a physical separation. People can't easily identify someone's accent or dialect through social media, unless the words used are known to be of a specific dialect. To be able to communicate easily through social media then, abbreviations and emojis come into play. In a way, they are a kind of lingua franca in its own. Will society at one point use abbreviations in daily life, as most people would understand them?

What power and prestige is associated with these new varieties of English? It is all happening so quickly that it is difficult to be sure; there have been so few studies. But impressionistically, we can see several of these new linguistic features achieving an increasingly public profile, in their respective countries. Words become used less self-consciously in the national press – no longer being put in inverted commas, for example, or given a gloss. They come to be adopted, often at first with some effort, then more naturally, by first-language speakers of English in the locality. Indeed, the canons of local political correctness, in the best sense of that phrase,

may foster a local usage, giving it more prestige than it could ever have dreamed of – a good example is the contemporary popularity in New Zealand English of Maori words (and the occasional Maori grammatical feature, such as the dropping of the definite article before the people name Maori itself). And, above all, the local words begin to be used at the prestigious levels of society – by politicians, religious leaders, socialites, pop musicians and others. Using local words is then no longer to be seen as slovenly or ignorant, within a country; it is respectable; it may even be ‘cool’.

In conclusion, it is impossible to predict change in the English language. All we can do is analyse the past changes and base our speculations on that. However, I personally think that we find ourselves living in an environment that is encouraging language change, for the better, or the worse.

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